

International Workshop

"New Horizons: Education - Generation - Technologies"

Hybrid – online & in-person

August 16, 2024, Cambridge, UNITED KINGDOM

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i> <i>New Horizons in Education for the Next Generation: Advancing Learning Innovations, Digital Pedagogies, and Lifelong Skill Development in a Rapidly Evolving World</i>	08.45-09.15
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i> <i>New Horizons in Generation Technologies: Pioneering Next-Gen Innovations at the Crossroads of Renewable Energy, AI, and Sustainable Infrastructure for a Resilient Future</i>	09.15-10.45
Q & A	10.45-11.00
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – Education, Generations, and Emerging Technologies</i> <i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i> <i>Education for Future Generations: Leveraging Emerging Technologies to Transform Learning and Development</i>	11.00-11.30
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i> <i>Transforming Education for Future Generations: Integrating Emerging Technologies to Revolutionize Learning and Human Development</i>	11.30-12.00

<p><i>Session 2 – Education for a New Generation: Emerging Technologies</i></p> <p><i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences</i></p> <p><i>Austria</i></p> <p><i>Education for a New Generation: Integrating Emerging Technologies to Redefine Learning Experiences and Foster Future-Ready Skills</i></p> <p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Education for a New Generation: Harnessing Emerging Technologies to Transform Learning Experiences and Equip Future Leaders with Essential Skills</i></p>	<p>11.00-11.30</p> <p>11.30-12.00</p>
<p>Coffee break</p>	<p>12.00-12.15</p>
<p><i>Session 1 – Education, Generations, and Emerging Technologies</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Revolutionizing Education for Future Generations: Employing Emerging Technologies to Redefine Learning Paradigms and Propel Human Development</i></p> <p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Transforming Education for the Next Generation: Leveraging Emerging Technologies to Redesign Learning Paradigms and Accelerate Human Development</i></p>	<p>12.15-12.45</p> <p>12.45-13.15</p>
<p><i>Session 2 – Education for a New Generation: Emerging Technologies</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Education for a New Generation: Leveraging Emerging Technologies to Innovate Learning Models and Prepare Future Leaders for Global Challenges</i></p> <p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Education for a New Generation: Harnessing Emerging Technologies to Redesign Learning Models and Equip Future Leaders to Navigate Global Challenges</i></p>	<p>12.15-12.45</p> <p>12.45-13.15</p>
<p>Q&A</p>	<p>13.15-13.45</p>

CBM International University USA
Akademos Learning UK
9462-9755 Quebec CA & AT (Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences)

Concluding remarks	13.45-14.00
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Location: Wellington House, East Road, Cambridge, CB1 1BH, United Kingdom